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Towards the SDG Challenges

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T3-P-55-ORAL Wine against obesity – *Cabernet Sauvignon* wine as inhibitor of pancreatic lipase

Tatjana Majkić¹⁶¹, Ljilja Torović¹⁶², Ivana Beara¹⁶¹

KEYWORDS: Obesity; *Cabernet Sauvignon* wine; polyphenols; pancreatic lipase

INTRODUCTION:

According to the World Health Organization, worldwide obesity has almost tripled since 1975, and in 2016, more than 650 million adults were obese. One of the strategies to reduce this number is to support and promote healthy diet habits and regular physical activity. On the other hand, a great number of epidemiological studies pointed out the Mediterranean diet, rich in beverages with high content of polyphenols, as one of the healthiest diets.

OBJECTIVES:

The aim of this study was to compare the polyphenol profile of *Cabernet Sauvignon* wines from five European countries (France, Italy, Macedonia, Spain and Serbia) and their potential to inhibit pancreatic lipase, the enzyme involved in lipid metabolism. Inhibition of pancreatic lipase could reduce the hydrolysis and consequently absorption of fats, which could be one of the mechanisms to reduce obesity.

METHOD / DESIGN:

The content of total polyphenols, flavonoids, tannins and monomeric anthocyanins was measured by spectrophotometric methods. Comprehensive evaluation of the polyphenolic profile of wine samples was performed by HPLC-UV/VIS technique, including quantitative analysis of nine phenolic acids, six flavonoids, two stilbenes and five anthocyanin glucosides. Lipase inhibition assay was performed using porcine pancreatic lipase and 4-nitrophenyl palmitate as a substrate. After the end of the reaction, the absorbance of yellow-colored p-nitrophenol was measured. Orlistat, a standard inhibitor of lipase, was used as a positive control.

RESULTS:

In all analysed samples, gallic acid was the dominant phenolic acid (18.3-102.7 mg/L), catechin was the most abundant flavonoid (13.2-56.7 mg/L), while the malvidin-3-O-glucoside was the dominant anthocyanin. In general, moderate qualitative and quantitative differences among samples were found. All wine samples showed some potential to inhibit lipase, and IC50 values ranged from 4.76-10.2 mg/mL. However, in comparison with orlistat, standard inhibitor of lipase and well-known drug, wines have low activity.

CONCLUSIONS:

Obtained results confirmed that examined wines are a rich source of polyphenols and that wines from Serbia could be compared with renowned wines, such as French ones. Although examined wines did not strongly inhibit lipase, they could, at least partially, contribute to overall health benefits.

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